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Another class of nonterminating ${}_3F_2$ -series with a free argument

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Abstract

By means of the linearization method, we evaluate another class of nonterminating ${}_3F_2$ -series with a free argument x and two perturbing integer parameters m and n .

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1 Introduction and motivation

There has always been a strong interest in discovering novel summation formulae for (generalized) hypergeometric series due to their broad variety of applications in mathematics, physics, and computer science (see [5–7, 13, 14, 19–21, 23]). The purpose of this paper is to evaluate, in closed forms, the following class of nonterminating ${}_3F_2$ -series with a free variable x (with $|x| < 1$ for convergence) and two perturbing integer parameters m and n :

$$\Omega_{m,n}(a, x) := {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2} + m, & 3a + n \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right], \quad (1)$$

where, according to Bailey [2, §2.1], the classical hypergeometric series reads as

$${}_{1+p}F_p \left[\begin{matrix} a_0, & a_1, \dots, a_p \\ & b_1, \dots, b_p \end{matrix} \middle| z \right] = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a_0)_k (a_1)_k \cdots (a_p)_k}{k! (b_1)_k \cdots (b_p)_k} z^k.$$

Denote by $\mathbb{Z}$ and $\mathbb{N}$, respectively, sets of integers and natural numbers with $\mathbb{N}_0 = \{0\} \cup \mathbb{N}$. For indeterminate y and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the rising and falling factorials are defined by the following quotients of Euler's Γ -function:

$$(x)_n = \frac{\Gamma(x+n)}{\Gamma(x)} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle x \rangle_n = \frac{\Gamma(1+x)}{\Gamma(1+x-n)},$$

where the multiparameter notation for the former one will be abbreviated to

$$\left[\begin{matrix} A, B, \dots, C \\ \alpha, \beta, \dots, \gamma \end{matrix} \right]_n = \frac{(A)_n (B)_n \cdots (C)_n}{(\alpha)_n (\beta)_n \cdots (\gamma)_n}.$$

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Our work is motivated by Lambert’s binomial series (see Riordan [22, §4.5] and [1, 8–10, 15, 20]) which is well known in classical analysis. Let u and v be the two variables related through the equation $u = v/(1 + v)^\beta$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_\alpha(u) &:= (1 + v)^\alpha = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + k\beta} \binom{\alpha + k\beta}{k} u^k, \\ \psi_\alpha(u) &:= \frac{(1 + v)^{\alpha+1}}{1 + v - \beta v} = \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\alpha + k\beta}{k} u^k. \end{aligned}$$

By the bisection of series, we have further four generating functions

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 2\beta k} \binom{\alpha + 2\beta k}{2k} u^{2k} &= \frac{\phi_\alpha(u) + \phi_\alpha(-u)}{2}, \\ \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\alpha + 2\beta k}{2k} u^{2k} &= \frac{\psi_\alpha(u) + \psi_\alpha(-u)}{2}; \\ \sum_{k=0}^\infty \frac{\alpha}{\alpha + \beta(2k + 1)} \binom{\alpha + \beta(2k + 1)}{2k + 1} u^{2k+1} &= \frac{\phi_\alpha(u) - \phi_\alpha(-u)}{2}, \\ \sum_{k=0}^\infty \binom{\alpha + \beta(2k + 1)}{2k + 1} u^{2k+1} &= \frac{\psi_\alpha(u) - \psi_\alpha(-u)}{2}. \end{aligned}$$

Specifying with $\beta = \frac{3}{2}$, making the replacements $u \rightarrow \frac{2x}{3\sqrt{3}}$, $v \rightarrow y$, and then letting

$$\alpha \rightarrow 3a - 1, \alpha \rightarrow 3a - 2, \alpha \rightarrow 3a - \frac{5}{2}, \alpha \rightarrow 3a - \frac{7}{2},$$

respectively, in the above four equations, we get four hypergeometric formulae:

$$\begin{aligned} {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] &= \frac{1}{2} \{ (1 + y_+)^{3a-1} + (1 + y_-)^{3a-1} \}, & [\Omega_{0,0}] \\ {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a - 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] &= \frac{(1 + y_+)^{3a-1}}{2 - y_+} + \frac{(1 + y_-)^{3a-1}}{2 - y_-}; & [\Omega_{0,-1}] \\ {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{3}{2}, & 3a - 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] &= \frac{(1 + y_+)^{3a-1}}{(6a - 5)y_+} + \frac{(1 + y_-)^{3a-1}}{(6a - 5)y_-}, & [\Omega_{1,-1}] \\ {}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{3}{2}, & 3a - 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] &= \frac{(1 + y_+)^{3a-1}}{(3a - 2)(2 - y_+)y_+} + \frac{(1 + y_-)^{3a-1}}{(3a - 2)(2 - y_-)y_-}. & [\Omega_{1,-2}] \end{aligned}$$

Here and forth, x and y are two variables related via equations

$$\pm x = \frac{3\sqrt{3}y_\pm}{2\sqrt{(1 + y_\pm)^3}}, \tag{2}$$

where $y_\pm$ are computed from x through the fundamental algebraic relationship

$$\frac{2x}{3\sqrt{3}} = \frac{y}{(1 + y)^{3/2}} \quad \text{or equivalently} \quad \left(\frac{2x}{y} \right)^2 = \left(\frac{3}{1 + y} \right)^3.$$

Recall that the hypergeometric ${}_3F_2(x^2)$ -series converge (generically) only if their argument is less than 1 in magnitude. Therefore x is restricted to $(-1, 1)$. There are exactly two solutions y_+ and y_- of the above equation in the region $(-1/4, 2)$ whenever x satisfies $-1 < x < 1$. By equating both members of the last equation to t^6 , we can parameterize the algebraic “ $x-y$ curve” by rational functions:

$$x = \frac{t}{2}(3 - t^2) \quad \text{and} \quad y = \frac{3 - t^2}{t^2}.$$

The portions of the curve with $t \in (-2, -1)$ and $t \in (1, 2)$ lie, in the “ $x-y$ plane”, in the abovementioned region. For any x , the corresponding $y_{\pm}$ are the y -coordinates of the points (x, y) that lie on these two branches that are illustrated in the Fig. 1.

The four identities of ${}_3F_2$ -series highlighted in the last page are not isolated examples. As we shall show, there exists a large number of closed formulae for the series $\Omega_{m,n}$. By means of the linearization method (cf. [3, 4, 11, 12, 16–18]), we shall reduce in the next section, for $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the series $\Omega_{m,n}$ to $\Omega_{m',0}$ with $m' < 0$. Then this last series will be evaluated in Sect. 3 via differential operators. The conclusive theorem affirms that, for all the $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the nonterminating $\Omega_{m,n}$ -series can be always evaluated explicitly in terms of a finite number of algebraic functions in $y_{\pm}$. Finally, by making use of *Mathematica* commands, 26 closed formulae are presented as exemplification.

2 Linearization method

By means of the linearization method, we shall establish, in this section, three reduction formulae that express ultimately the series $\Omega_{m,n}$ with $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ in terms of the series $\Omega_{m',0}$, but with $m' < 0$.

2.1 $m > 0$

By employing the Chu–Vandermonde formula on binomial convolutions, it is routine to prove the following linear representation lemma.

Lemma 1 (Linear representation) *For a natural number m and a variable y , the following linear relation holds:*

$$\langle y \rangle_m = \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{m}{i} \langle A + y \rangle_{m-i} \langle A \rangle_i.$$

Now specifying in this lemma the parameters

$$y = k \quad \text{and} \quad A = 3a - m + n - 1,$$

we get the equality

$$\langle k \rangle_m = \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{m}{i} \langle 3a - m + n - 1 + k \rangle_{m-i} \langle 3a - m + n - 1 \rangle_i.$$

By inserting this relation in the $\Omega_{m,n}$ -series, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{m,n}(a, x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_k (a - \frac{1}{3})_k (a + \frac{1}{3})_k}{k! (\frac{1}{2} + m)_k (3a + n)_k} x^{2k} \\ &= \sum_{k=m}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{k-m} (a - \frac{1}{3})_{k-m} (a + \frac{1}{3})_{k-m}}{(k-m)! (\frac{1}{2} + m)_{k-m} (3a + n)_{k-m}} x^{2k-2m} \\ &\quad \times \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{m}{i} \frac{\langle 3a - m + n - 1 + k \rangle_{m-i} \langle 3a - m + n - 1 \rangle_i}{\langle k \rangle_m}. \end{aligned}$$

Observing that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\langle 3a - m + n - 1 + k \rangle_{m-i}}{(3a + n)_{k-m}} &= \frac{(1 - 3a - n)_{2m}}{(3a - 2m + n)_{k+i}}, \\ \frac{(a)_{k-m} (a - \frac{1}{3})_{k-m} (a + \frac{1}{3})_{k-m}}{(k-m)! \langle k \rangle_m} &= (-27)^m \frac{(a - m)_k (a - m - \frac{1}{3})_k (a - m + \frac{1}{3})_k}{k! (2 - 3a)_{3m}}; \end{aligned}$$

we can reformulate the double sum

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{m,n}(a, x) &= \left(-\frac{27}{x^2} \right)^m \frac{(\frac{1}{2})_m (1 - 3a - n)_{2m}}{(2 - 3a)_{3m}} \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{m}{i} \frac{(3a - m + n - 1)_i}{(3a - 2m + n)_i} \\ &\quad \times \sum_{k=m}^{\infty} \left[\begin{matrix} a - m, & a - m - \frac{1}{3}, & a - m + \frac{1}{3} \\ 1, & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a - 2m + n + i \end{matrix} \right]_k x^{2k}. \end{aligned}$$

Expressing the last sum with respect to k in terms of $\Omega_{0,m+n+i}(a - m, x)$, we derive the first reduction formula.

Proposition 2 ($m \in \mathbb{N}_0$ and $n \in \mathbb{Z}$)

$$\Omega_{m,n}(a, x) = \left(-\frac{27}{x^2} \right)^m \frac{(\frac{1}{2})_m (1 - 3a - n)_{2m}}{(2 - 3a)_{3m}} \sum_{i=0}^m (-1)^i \binom{m}{i} \frac{(3a - m + n - 1)_i}{(3a - 2m + n)_i}$$

$$\times \left\{ \Omega_{0,m+n+i}(a-m,x) - \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \frac{(3a-3m-1)_{3k}}{(2k)!(3a-2m+n+i)_k} \left(\frac{4x^2}{27}\right)^k \right\}.$$

2.2 $n < 0$

Analogously, we can also prove, without difficulty, another linear representation lemma.

Lemma 3 (Linear representation) *For a negative integer n and a variable y , the following linear relation holds:*

$$(A+y)_{-n} = \sum_{i=0}^{-n} \binom{-n}{i} (B+y)_i (A-B+i)_{-n-i}.$$

Under the parameter specification

$$y = k, \quad A = 3a + n, \quad B = m - \frac{1}{2},$$

the equality in Lemma 3 can be restated as

$$(3a+n+k)_{-n} = \sum_{i=0}^{-n} \binom{-n}{i} \left\langle m+k-\frac{1}{2} \right\rangle_i \left(3a+n-m+\frac{1}{2}+i \right)_{-n-i}.$$

By putting this relation inside the $\Omega_{m,n}$ -series, we can manipulate the double sum

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{m,n}(a,x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_k (a-\frac{1}{3})_k (a+\frac{1}{3})_k}{k! (\frac{1}{2}+m)_k (3a+n)_{k-n}} x^{2k} \\ &\quad \times \sum_{i=0}^{-n} \binom{-n}{i} \left\langle m+k-\frac{1}{2} \right\rangle_i \left(3a+n-m+\frac{1}{2}+i \right)_{-n-i} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{-n} \binom{-n}{i} \left(3a+n-m+\frac{1}{2}+i \right)_{-n-i} \\ &\quad \times \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left\langle m+k-\frac{1}{2} \right\rangle_i \frac{(a)_k (a-\frac{1}{3})_k (a+\frac{1}{3})_k}{k! (\frac{1}{2}+m)_k (3a+n)_{k-n}} x^{2k} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{-n} \binom{-n}{i} \frac{(\frac{1}{2}+m-i)_i (3a)_n}{(3a-m+\frac{1}{2})_{n+i}} \\ &\quad \times \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_k (a-\frac{1}{3})_k (a+\frac{1}{3})_k}{k! (\frac{1}{2}+m-i)_k (3a)_k} x^{2k}. \end{aligned}$$

Writing the last sum by $\Omega_{m-i,0}(a,x)$, we get the second reduction formula.

Proposition 4 ($m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$ with $n < 0$)

$$\Omega_{m,n}(a,x) = \sum_{i=0}^{-n} (-1)^i \binom{-n}{i} \frac{(\frac{1}{2}-m)_i (3a)_n}{(3a-m+\frac{1}{2})_{n+i}} \Omega_{m-i,0}(a,x).$$

2.3 $n > 0$

The next linear relation comes from a limiting case of a known one. Dividing by A^m equation (3.1) in [17, Lemma 3.1] and then letting $A \rightarrow \infty$, we get the following linearization lemma.

Lemma 5 (Linear representation) *For a natural number n and a variable y , the following linear relation holds:*

$$1 = \sum_{i=0}^n (B + y)_{n-i} (3C + 3y)_i X_n^i, \tag{3}$$

where the coefficients X_n^i are independent of the variable y and given explicitly by the two expressions

$$\begin{aligned} X_n^i &= \sum_{j=0}^i \frac{(-1)^{n-i+j}}{i!} \binom{i}{j} \frac{3C - 3B + 3n - 2i}{3(C - B + \frac{i}{3})_{n-i+1}} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{n-i} \frac{(-1)^{n-i+j}}{(n-i)!} \binom{n-i}{j} \frac{3C - 3B + 3n - 2i}{(3C - 3B + 3j)_{i+1}}. \end{aligned}$$

Specifying in Lemma 5 the parameters

$$y = k, \quad B = 3a + n - 1, \quad C = a - \frac{1}{3},$$

the equality corresponding to (3) becomes

$$1 = \sum_{i=0}^n (3a + n + k - 1)_{n-i} (3a - 1 + 3k)_i \mathcal{X}_n^i \tag{4}$$

with the coefficients $\mathcal{X}_n^i$ being determined by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{X}_n^i &= \sum_{j=0}^i \frac{(-1)^{n-i+j}}{i!} \binom{i}{j} \frac{2 - 6a - 2i}{3(\frac{2}{3} - 2a - n + \frac{i}{3})_{n-i+1}} \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{n-i} \frac{(-1)^{n-i+j}}{(n-i)!} \binom{n-i}{j} \frac{2 - 6a - 2i}{(2 - 6a - 3n + 3j)_{i+1}}. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

By inserting this relation (5) in the $\Omega_{m,n}$ -series, we get the double sum

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{m,n}(a, x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_k (a - \frac{1}{3})_k (a + \frac{1}{3})_k}{k! (\frac{1}{2} + m)_k (3a + n)_k} x^{2k} \\ &\quad \times \sum_{i=0}^n (3a + n + k - 1)_{n-i} (3a - 1 + 3k)_i \mathcal{X}_n^i \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^n (3a - 1)_i (3a + i)_{n-i} \mathcal{X}_n^i \end{aligned}$$

$$\times \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \begin{bmatrix} a + \frac{i}{3} - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{i}{3}, & a + \frac{i}{3} + \frac{1}{3} \\ 1, & \frac{1}{2} + m, & 3a + i \end{bmatrix}_k x^{2k}.$$

Expressing the last sum by $\Omega_{m,0}(a + \frac{i}{3}, x)$, we have the third reduction formula.

Proposition 6 *Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and the connection coefficients $\{\mathcal{X}_n^i\}$ be given by (5). Then the following formula holds:*

$$\Omega_{m,n}(a, x) = \sum_{i=0}^n \mathcal{X}_n^i (3a - 1)_i (3a + i)_{n-i} \Omega_{m,0}\left(a + \frac{i}{3}, x\right).$$

3 Conclusive theorem and examples

For a given integer pair $\{m, n\}$, we can express the $\Omega_{m,n}$ -series, by making use of Propositions 2, 4, and 6, in terms of $\Omega_{m',0}$ -series with $m' \leq 0$. Therefore it remains to evaluate this last series. This will be done by utilizing differential operations. Suppose that $f(x)$ is a differentiable function. Define the operator δ by

$$\delta f(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \left\{ \frac{f(x)}{x} \right\}.$$

Then it is not hard to check that

$$\begin{aligned} \delta \Omega_{0,0}(a, x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (2k - 1) \begin{bmatrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ 1, & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a \end{bmatrix}_k x^{2k-2} = \frac{-1}{x^2} \Omega_{-1,0}(a, x), \\ \delta^2 \Omega_{0,0}(a, x) &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (3 - 2k) \begin{bmatrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ 1, & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a \end{bmatrix}_k x^{2k-4} = \frac{3}{x^4} \Omega_{-2,0}(a, x). \end{aligned}$$

Proceeding by induction, we can show that

$$\begin{aligned} \delta^n \Omega_{0,0}(a, x) &= (-1)^{n-1} (2n - 3)!! \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \begin{bmatrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ 1, & \frac{3}{2} - n, & 3a \end{bmatrix}_k (2k - 2n + 1) x^{2k-2n} \\ &= \frac{(-1)^n (2n - 1)!!}{x^{2n}} \Omega_{-n,0}(a, x). \end{aligned}$$

Recalling that

$$\Omega_{0,0}(a, x) = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ (1 + y_+)^{3a-1} + (1 + y_-)^{3a-1} \right\}$$

and then relabeling n by $-m$, we get the following expression.

Proposition 7 *For $m < 0$ and the three variables $\{x, y_{\pm}\}$ related by (2), the following formula holds:*

$$\Omega_{m,0}(a, x) = \frac{(-2/x^2)^m}{2(\frac{1}{2})_{-m}} \delta^{-m} \left\{ (1 + y_+)^{3a-1} + (1 + y_-)^{3a-1} \right\}.$$

As an anonymous referee pointed out, instead of Proposition 4 the case $n < 0$ can be alternatively treated by repeatedly applying the operator δ to the initial function $x^{6a-1}\Omega_{0,0}(a, x)$.

Summing up, for any given pair of integers m and n , the series $\Omega_{m,n}(a, x)$ can be evaluated by carrying out the following procedure:

- *Step-A:* If $m > 0$, write $\Omega_{m,n}(a, x)$, by means of Proposition 2, in terms of $\Omega_{0,n'}(a - m, x)$; then go to *Step-B*.
- *Step-B:* For $m \leq 0$ and $n \neq 0$, apply Propositions 4 and 6 to express $\Omega_{m,n}(a, x)$ as $\Omega_{m',0}(a', x)$ with $m' \leq m$; then go to *Step-C*.
- *Step-C:* Finally, for $m \leq 0$ and $n = 0$, evaluate $\Omega_{m,0}(a, x)$, according to Proposition 7, by differentiating $\Omega_{0,0}(a, x)$.

Therefore, we have shown the following general conclusion.

Theorem 8 *For all the $m, n \in \mathbb{Z}$, the nonterminating $\Omega_{m,n}$ -series are always evaluable explicitly in a finite number of terms of algebraic functions in $y_{\pm}$.*

Based on Propositions 2, 4, 6, and 7, we have devised appropriately *Mathematica* commands that are employed to evaluate $\Omega_{m,n}$ in closed forms for any specific integer pair “ m, n ”. Apart from the four formulae anticipated in the Introduction, we highlight further 26 elegant formulae as exemplification.

Example 1 ($m = 0$ and $n = 1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a + 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{2(6a + 1)} \{1 + 6a + y - 3ay\}.$$

Example 2 ($m = 0$ and $n = 2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a + 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{4(2a + 1)(3a + 2)(6a + 1)} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 4 + 96a^2 + 72a^3 + 4y + 10ay - 42a^2y \\ + 38a - 72a^3y - ay^2 - 3a^2y^2 + 18a^3y^2 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 3 ($m = 0$ and $n = -2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a - 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}(8 - 12a - 7y + 6ay)}{(3a - 2)(y - 2)^3}.$$

Example 4 ($m = 0$ and $n = -3$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a - 3 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{2(1+y)^{3a-1}}{(a-1)(3a-2)(2-y)^5} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 16 - 40a + 24a^2 - 29y + 58ay \\ -24a^2y + 15y^2 - 19ay^2 + 6a^2y^2 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 5 ($m = 1$ and $n = 0$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{3}{2}, & 3a \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}(4-12a-5y+6ay)}{6(1-2a)(6a-5)y}.$$

Example 6 ($m = 1$ and $n = 1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{3}{2}, & 3a + 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{-3(1+y)^{3a-1}}{32y(3a-\frac{5}{2})_4} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 8a + 24a^2 - 144a^3 + 5y + 4ay - 132a^2y \\ +144a^3y + 5y^2 - 31ay^2 + 60a^2y^2 - 36a^3y^2 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 7 ($m = 1$ and $n = -3$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{3}{2}, & 3a - 3 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{2(1+y)^{3a-1}(7-6a-5y+3ay)}{3y(a-1)(3a-2)(y-2)^3}.$$

Example 8 ($m = -1$ and $n = 0$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{2(2-y)} \{2+y-6ay\}.$$

Example 9 ($m = -1$ and $n = 1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a + 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + y)^{3a-1} \{1 + y - 3ay\}.$$

Example 10 ($m = -1$ and $n = 2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a + 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{4(3a + 2)} \{4 + 6a + 4y - 6ay - 18a^2y - 3ay^2 + 9a^2y^2\}.$$

Example 11 ($m = -1$ and $n = 3$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a + 3 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{4(a + 1)(6a + 7)} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 14 - 16ay - 66a^2y - 36a^3y - 14ay^2 + 30a^2y^2 \\ + 26a + 12a^2 + 14y + 36a^3y^2 + ay^3 - 9a^3y^3 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 12 ($m = -1$ and $n = -1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a - 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{(2 - y)^3} \{4 - 2y - 12ay - 3y^2 + 6ay^2\}.$$

Example 13 ($m = -1$ and $n = -2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a - 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{(3a - 2)(y - 2)^5} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 32 - 24ay + 144a^2y + 168ay^2 - 144a^2y^2 \\ - 48a - 48y + 35y^3 - 72ay^3 + 36a^2y^3 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 14 ($m = 2$ and $n = -1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{5}{2}, & 3a - 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{3(1+y)^{3a-1}}{16y^3(3a - \frac{11}{2})_4} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 20 - 192ay + 72a^2y + 120ay^2 \\ -24a + 110y - 99y^2 - 36a^2y^2 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 15 ($m = 2$ and $n = -2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{5}{2}, & 3a - 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{3(1+y)^{3a-1}(2 + 11y - 6ay)}{4y^3(2 - 3a)(3a - \frac{11}{2})_2}.$$

Example 16 ($m = 2$ and $n = -3$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{5}{2}, & 3a - 3 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{6(1+y)^{3a-1}(1 + 5y - 3ay)}{(3a - 3)_2(6a - 11)(y - 2)y^3}.$$

Example 17 ($m = -2$ and $n = 0$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{3}{2}, & 3a \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{6(2-y)^3} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 24 - 12y - 72ay - 14y^2 + y^3 \\ +72ay^2 + 72a^2y^2 - 36a^2y^3 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 18 ($m = -2$ and $n = 1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{3}{2}, & 3a + 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{2(2-y)} \{ 2 + y - 6ay - y^2 + ay^2 + 6a^2y^2 \}.$$

Example 19 ($m = -2$ and $n = -1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ -\frac{3}{2}, & 3a - 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{(2-y)^5} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 16 - 24y - 48ay + 88ay^2 + 48a^2y^2 + 20y^3 \\ -16ay^3 - 48a^2y^3 + y^4 - 8ay^4 + 12a^2y^4 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 20 ($m = -2$ and $n = 2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ -\frac{3}{2}, & 3a + 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{4(3a+2)} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 4 + 6a + 4y - 6ay - 18a^2y \\ -5ay^2 + 9a^2y^2 + 18a^3y^2 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 21 ($m = -2$ and $n = 3$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ -\frac{3}{2}, & 3a + 3 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{12(a+1)} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 6 + 6a + 6y - 12ay - 18a^2y - 8ay^2 \\ +18a^2y^2 + 18a^3y^2 + ay^3 - 9a^3y^3 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 22 ($m = -3$ and $n = 1$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ -\frac{5}{2}, & 3a + 1 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{10(2-y)^3} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 40 - 120ay - 30y^2 + 132ay^2 + 144a^2y^2 + 25y^3 - 22ay^3 \\ -20y - 180a^2y^3 - 72a^3y^3 - 5y^4 - ay^4 + 36a^2y^4 + 36a^3y^4 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 23 ($m = -3$ and $n = 2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ -\frac{5}{2}, & 3a + 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1+y)^{3a-1}}{20(3a+2)(2-y)} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 40 - 90ay - 180a^2y - 20y^2 - 24ay^2 + 180a^2y^2 + 35ay^3 \\ +60a + 20y + 216a^3y^2 - 33a^2y^3 - 180a^3y^3 - 108a^4y^3 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 24 ($m = -3$ and $n = 3$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{5}{2}, & 3a + 3 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{20(a + 1)} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 10 - 20ay - 30a^2y - 14ay^2 + 30a^2y^2 + 36a^3y^2 \\ +10a + 10y + 3ay^3 + 2a^2y^3 - 27a^3y^3 - 18a^4y^3 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 25 ($m = 3$ and $n = -3$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{7}{2}, & 3a - 3 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{-45(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{8y^5(3a - 3)_2(3a - \frac{17}{2})_4} \left\{ \begin{matrix} 22 + 187y - 168ay + 36a^2y + 425y^2 \\ -12a - 575ay^2 + 252a^2y^2 - 36a^3y^2 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

Example 26 ($m = 3$ and $n = -2$)

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{7}{2}, & 3a - 2 \end{matrix} \middle| x^2 \right] = w(y_+) + w(y_-),$$

where

$$w(y) = \frac{45(1 + y)^{3a-1}}{32y^5(2 - 3a)(3a - \frac{17}{2})_5} \times \left\{ \begin{matrix} 72 - 48a - 624ay + 144a^2y + 1190y^2 - 1916ay^2 + 936a^2y^2 \\ +612y - 144a^3y^2 - 1105y^3 + 1342ay^3 - 540a^2y^3 + 72a^3y^3 \end{matrix} \right\}.$$

These identities are valid for all the x and y tied by (2) under the conditions $|x| < 1$ and $-1/4 < y < 2$. When x is assigned to particular values, they may produce strange evaluation formulae. We limit ourselves to recording three groups of such formulae.

- Series with $\{x, y_+, y_-\} = \{\sqrt{\frac{3^5}{7^3}}, \frac{3}{4}, -\frac{2}{9}\}$.

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a \end{matrix} \middle| \frac{3^5}{7^3} \right] = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \left(\frac{7}{4}\right)^{3a-1} + \left(\frac{7}{9}\right)^{3a-1} \right\}, \tag{Ω_{0,0}}$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a - \frac{1}{3}, & a + \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{3}{2}, & 3a - 1 \end{matrix} \middle| \frac{3^5}{7^3} \right] = \frac{7^{3a-1}}{6(6a - 5)} \{2^{5-6a} - 3^{5-6a}\}, \tag{Ω_{1,-1}}$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & \frac{1}{2}, & 3a + 1 \end{matrix} \middle| \frac{3^5}{7^3} \right] = \frac{7^{3a-1}}{2(6a + 1)} \left\{ \frac{15a + 7}{2^{6a}} + \frac{60a + 7}{3^{6a}} \right\}, \tag{Ω_{0,1}}$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[\begin{matrix} a, & a + \frac{1}{3}, & a - \frac{1}{3} \\ & -\frac{1}{2}, & 3a + 1 \end{matrix} \middle| \frac{3^5}{7^3} \right] = \frac{7^{3a-1}}{2} \left\{ \frac{6a + 7}{3^{6a}} - \frac{9a - 7}{2^{6a}} \right\}. \tag{Ω_{-1,1}}$$

- Series with $\{x, y_+, y_-\} = \{2\sqrt{\frac{3^5}{13^3}}, \frac{4}{9}, -\frac{3}{16}\}$.

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a - \frac{1}{3}, a + \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{4 \cdot 3^5}{13^3} \right] = \frac{9}{14} \left(\frac{13}{9} \right)^{3a-1} + \frac{16}{35} \left(\frac{13}{16} \right)^{3a-1}, \quad [\Omega_{0,-1}]$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a - \frac{1}{3}, a + \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{4 \cdot 3^5}{13^3} \right] = \frac{13^{3a-1}}{3a-2} \left\{ \frac{3^{6-6a}}{56} - \frac{4^{6-6a}}{105} \right\}, \quad [\Omega_{1,-2}]$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{4 \cdot 3^5}{13^3} \right] = \frac{13^{3a-1}}{24(3a - \frac{5}{2})_2} \left\{ \frac{63a - 12}{9^{3a-1}} - \frac{210a - 79}{16^{3a-1}} \right\}, \quad [\Omega_{1,0}]$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{4 \cdot 3^5}{13^3} \right] = \frac{13^{3a-1}/(3a-2)}{2304(3a - \frac{11}{2})_2} \left\{ \frac{24a - 62}{27^{2a-3}} + \frac{18a - 1}{64^{2a-3}} \right\}. \quad [\Omega_{2,-2}]$$

- Series with $\{x, y_+, y_-\} = \{5\sqrt{\frac{3^5}{19^3}}, \frac{10}{9}, -\frac{6}{25}\}$.

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{25 \cdot 3^5}{19^3} \right] = \frac{19^{3a-1}}{3a-2} \left\{ \frac{24a - 1}{256 \cdot 3^{6a-6}} + \frac{168a - 121}{87,808 \cdot 5^{6a-6}} \right\}, \quad [\Omega_{0,-2}]$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{25 \cdot 3^5}{19^3} \right] = \frac{19^{3a-1}}{(3a-2)(a-1)} \left\{ \frac{24a - 13}{2560 \cdot 3^{6a-7}} + \frac{205 - 168a}{1,580,544 \cdot 5^{6a-8}} \right\}, \quad [\Omega_{1,-3}]$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{25 \cdot 3^5}{19^3} \right] = 19^{3a-1} \left\{ \frac{7 - 15a}{4 \cdot 9^{3a-1}} + \frac{9a + 11}{28 \cdot 25^{3a-1}} \right\}, \quad [\Omega_{-1,0}]$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| \frac{25 \cdot 3^5}{19^3} \right] = \frac{19^{3a-1}}{(3a-3)_2(6a-11)} \left\{ \frac{30a - 59}{4000 \cdot 3^{6a-9}} + \frac{18a - 5}{2016 \cdot 5^{6a-8}} \right\}. \quad [\Omega_{2,-3}]$$

To our knowledge, the formulae presented in this paper for $\Omega_{m,n}(a, x)$ (when x is a free variable) have not appeared previously. Exceptions are about $\Omega_{0,0}$, $\Omega_{1,-1}$, and $\Omega_{0,1}$. Their particular cases with $\{x, y_+, y_-\} = \{1, 2, -1/4\}$ have been recorded by Milgram in his compendium [21, Equations 25, 30, 31]:

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| 1 \right] = \frac{3^{3a-1}(1 + 4^{1-3a})}{2},$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| 1 \right] = \frac{3^{3a-1}}{(6a-5)} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} - 4^{2-3a} \right\},$$

$${}_3F_2 \left[a, a + \frac{1}{3}, a - \frac{1}{3} \middle| 1 \right] = \frac{27^a}{6a+1} \left\{ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{9a+1}{2^{6a+1}} \right\}.$$

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Authors' contributions

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